

Proof of the Pythagorean theorem through the Basic Trigonometric Identity

16.11.2024, Denisov Ivan

Russia, Denissoviv@yandex.ru

I. the main decision

$$1. \quad 1 = \cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha = \frac{a^2}{c^2} + \frac{b^2}{c^2} = \frac{a^2 + b^2}{c^2}$$

$$2. \Rightarrow \boxed{a^2 + b^2 = c^2}$$

II. auxiliary solution

$$\begin{aligned} 1. \quad \sin \alpha &= \frac{b}{c} \Rightarrow \sin^2 \alpha = \frac{b^2}{c^2} \\ 2. \quad \cos \alpha &= \frac{a}{c} \Rightarrow \cos^2 \alpha = \frac{a^2}{c^2} \end{aligned} \quad \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} 1. \\ 2. \end{aligned}} \right\} \Rightarrow$$

$$3. \Rightarrow \sin^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \alpha = \frac{b^2}{c^2} + \frac{a^2}{c^2} = \frac{b^2 + a^2}{c^2};$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 = \frac{b^2 + a^2}{c^2}$$

$$4. \Rightarrow \boxed{a^2 + b^2 = c^2}$$

Pythagoras' theorem is proven